

THE USE OF SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS FOR TEACHING HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN EFL

Language Teaching

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Abstract

The growing influence of foreign language in the context of globalization has attracted interest in finding the most appropriate techniques and strategies that contribute to the acquisition of a foreign language. Communication between the countries is already easier than before as a result of changes in science and technology. People try to learn different languages to communicate with other peoples. Being an international communication language, English is one of the languages for which there are high demands for learning. As a result, linguists have been trying to find new ways to learn it in a simple and effective way, paying attention to the modernization of teaching and learning methods and techniques as well as the teaching materials used. In order to preserve the student's interest in learning and to increase their ability of critical and aesthetic perception, teachers should give them the opportunity of practice, discussions, questions, and defending their controversial opinions on different opinions in class. The main reason for doing so is to maintain the motivation and interest of students and to avoid a boring hour with passive students.

Introduction

To make sure that learning becomes a highly educational activity, to the extent that it contributes to a person's growth and development considering the local and global context of which the student is part, it is necessary that teaching EFL is not an episodic event, fragmented, disconnected from the rest of the curriculum; it is crucial that it is designed identifying horizontal connections with other subjects and developing vertically the progress of knowledge and competences needed to pass from one order of schooling to another. The horizontal and vertical aspects of the English Language curriculum must also be read in the perspective of building a synergy connection between the formal learning, that student acquires in school, and the non-formal and informal learning, with which (s)he comes into contact with in everyday life. With regard to English language learning, this transversal dimension, that links the contexts of life and the student's learning, is very strong. Indeed, in everyday life (s) he interacts, even unconsciously, with linguistic expressions, terms, phrases, idioms in English, conveyed mostly by the media and the Internet, which can be quite very familiar to him/her because they already belong to the linguistic heritage. The latter does not represent a linguistic shock for the student, i.e., a refusal for all that (s) he does not fully understand about the new language. The habit of using words borrowed from other languages assumes an absolute naturalness and spontaneity, so they are not

perceived as “strange” because they are related to the common lexicon used in activities, situations and forms of interaction that are constantly present in everyday life.¹

Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

This review is intended to provide:

1. a sound theoretical and empirically informed basis for prototype development of supplementary material learning resources to support language teaching and learning
2. a sound theoretical and empirically informed basis for informing policy on teaching and learning English as foreign language
3. a basis for communication between the educational community and students on the subject of teaching and learning English language with the use of supplementary materials

This review describes ways to develop student language and literacy skills while engaged in scholarly content. Five major strategies are discussed

- **Building theoretical frameworks:** students must understand relationships between ideas. The authors suggest the use of schemas or interpretive frames; e.g., graphic organizers to help clarify connections between ideas.

- **Use of learning strategies:** students must learn to monitor their own learning in order to experience success.

- **Focus on reading:** teachers can clearly and definitely teach what good readers do in pre-, during- and post-reading tasks, and provide opportunities for students to respond to text.

- **Use of free reading:** free reading can build vocabulary and reading habits. Students may need to be taught how to select appropriate reading material for level and interest.

- **Moving beyond the text:** at the final opinion of a unit, students may be asked to re-examine or rethink ideas to gain deeper understanding. This approach will force students to return to the text and reflect on its meaning.²

Supplementary or additional materials are a very important aid for the English language teachers because they provide practice and information for areas students may have more difficulty understanding. The appropriate selection and use of materials not only contribute to improve instruction and performance but also to increase interest in and enthusiasm for learning by getting a funny and successful class. Visual, audio, audiovisual and online are considered supplementary materials to be used in the classrooms to guard against the dullness of falling into the same teaching old strategy and same source of learning content over and over again. Thinking

¹ B. Tomlinson, *Materials development in language teaching*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2011; J. Enver, (Eds.), *ElliE. Early Language Learning in Europe*, British Council, UK, 2011

² Crandall, J., Jaramillo, A., Olsen, L., & Peyton, J. K. (2002). Using cognitive strategies to develop English language and literacy. ERIC No. ED469970, <http://www.eric.ed.gov> (Accessed March 17, 2008)

about what has been said about the use of supplementary materials for achieving teaching learning goals, it is necessary to say that aspects like the influence of age, differences and motivation of learners, learning styles; and teaching techniques and contexts must be taken into account by teachers during the teaching process. It is helpful to refer to previous studies in order to have a clearer view of how supporting materials have been used and applied in different cases and contexts.

Teaching a foreign language refers to a learning program designed to make an individual skilled in the use of the English language by using techniques and methodologies to develop listening, speaking, reading, writing, and vocabulary skills. To make the chore of teaching a foreign language more effective and simple it is necessary to make it attractive to the students. It is accomplished by the use of easy vocabulary during the whole teaching process.³

It is well known that children tend to pick up easily any new language that they are rounded by. One of the advantages of learning a foreign language early is the pronunciation; however a disadvantage of learning a language early is the grammar and the ability of the size of learning vocabulary. Anyway it is proved that there are more advantages of learning a language early, for that reason each time elementary schools are implementing more programs. Also to teach well a foreign language depends on the time that will be invested by the teacher and the students.⁴

In a foreign language teachers have to let students to communicate effectively by using different communicative activities that give practice, improve motivation, and produce a learning context. Those activities are divided into functional activities that refers to develop the language in particular situations; social interaction activities in which language is used according to the social context where it is carried out; and listening activities that has to do with the action to use the language face to face.⁵

Research Methodology

The paper deals with the theoretical background of teaching methodology concerning English as foreign language learning with particular accent on methods that are applied for teaching high school students. This theoretical part is divided into two subcategories: the first one concerns the process of learning from the young learner's point of view, and the other one centers on the methodology of teaching. Moreover the work presents practical conclusions about the issue as well as useful and applicable materials for teachers who have high school students with learning difficulties in the classroom.

³ Jaegel, W. (2007). The importance of English as a second language. Retrieved from <http://wolfgangjaegel.articlesbase.com/education-articles/the-importance-of-english-asa-second-language-233057.html>

⁴ Dekeyser, R. M. (2006). Foreign language instruction: implementing the best teaching methods.

⁵ Littlewood, W. (1981) Communicative language teaching. Great Britain: Cambridge University Press.

Language teaching methodologies:

- The Direct Method

Teaching according to this method is done completely in the target language. The learner is not allowed to use his or her mother tongue. Grammar rules are avoided and there is focus on good pronunciation.

Characteristic features of the direct method are:

- teaching concepts and vocabulary through acting things out, real-life objects and other visual materials
- teaching grammar by using an inductive approach (i.e. having learners find out rules through the presentation of adequate linguistic forms in the target language)
- centrality of spoken language (including a native-like pronunciation)
- focus on question-answer patterns

- Grammar-translation

Learning is mostly by translation to and from the target language. Grammar rules are to be learned and long lists of vocabulary learned by heart. There is little or no importance and focus placed on developing oral ability.

- Audio-lingual

The theory behind this method is that learning a language means and owning habits. There is much practice of dialogues of every situation. New language is first heard and a lot drilled before being seen in its written form.

- The structural approach

This method sees language as a complex of grammatical rules which are to be learned one at a time in a set order. So for example the verb "to be" is introduced and practiced before the present continuous tense which uses "to be" as an auxiliary.

- Suggestopedia

The theory underlying this method is that a language can be owned only when the learner is willing to listen and has no mental blocks. By different methods it is suggested to the student that the language is easy - and in this way the mental blocks to learning are removed.

- *Total Physical Response (TPR)*

TPR works by having the learner respond to simple commands such as "Stand up", "Close your book", "Go to the window and open it." The method stresses the importance of sound-based understanding.

- *Communicative language teaching (CLT)*

The point of this method is to enable the learner to communicate effectively and appropriately in the different situations she would be likely to find herself in. The content of CLT courses are functions such as inviting, suggesting, complaining or ideas such as the expression of time, amount, location.

The Silent Way

This is so called because the aim of the teacher is to say as little as possible in order that the learner can be in control of what he wants to say. No use is made of the mother tongue.

- *Community Language Learning*

In this method attempts are made to build strong personal links between the teacher and student so that there are no blocks to learning. There is much talk in the mother tongue which is translated by the teacher for repetition by the student.

- *Immersion*

This goes along with a great extent to the situation we have at our school. ESL students are surrounded by the English language for the whole of the school day and expected to learn math, science, humanities etc. through the medium of the target language, English.

- *Task-based language learning*

The focus of the teaching is on the completion of a task which in itself is interesting to the learners. Learners use the language they already have to complete the task and there is little correction of errors.

- *The Natural Approach*

This approach, proposed by Professor S. Krashen, stresses the similarities between learning the first and second languages. There is no correction of mistakes. Learning takes place by the students being exposed to language that is understandable or made understandable to them.

- *The Lexical Syllabus*

This approach is based on a computer analysis of language which identifies the most common (and hence most useful) words in the language and their different uses. The syllabus

teaches these words in broadly the order of their frequency, and great importance and focus is placed on the use of authentic materials.⁶

Findings

The following research was done for the survey of use of authentic materials by the English language teachers of high schools in Skopje. The following findings can be drawn from it:

1. It has been found that only 50% of teachers are aware of authentic materials.
2. Most of the teachers use news papers as authentic materials.
3. It shows that it is more beneficial for those students whose educational background and previous knowledge is better.
4. Students have a positive attitude towards authentic materials.
5. According to the teachers using authentic materials, authentic materials are occasion of co-operation and motivation among students.
6. These materials promote ability of conversation and explanation of the students.
7. These materials make the teaching learning process interesting.

Summary, Conclusion and Recommendations

Certain conclusions were achieved. In the first instance, pre-service teachers have mainly positive perceptions of the presentation of basic skills. They consider that basic language skills are given in perfect balance between precision and fluency. On the other hand they think that course books help learners develop grammar and vocabulary knowledge. Endorse EFL teachers have some negative views of course books. For instance, they consider that various language teaching methods are not given in the book to improve speaking skills, and they do not help learners to improve their pronunciation skills in considerable contexts. Moreover, for teachers, course books do not include cultural elements exemplifying authentic language. They consider that the course books do not support students well in terms of structure and design, activities and tasks, language type, subject and content, since they think course book packages are not empowered along with curricula. These can be listed as institutions, teaching groups, working conditions, curriculum and teaching experiences. For example, the institution and classroom tend to have a greater influence in the way teachers use their textbooks. In addition, learning styles and the personal teaching differences affect their perceptions of course books.

⁶ <http://esl.fis.edu/teachers/support/method.htm>

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